

A SURVEY STUDY TO ASSESS KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES ABOUT OBESITY AMONG OBESE INDIVIDUALS

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ABSTRACT

Obesity has emerged as a critical global health issue, contributing to a wide range of chronic diseases and reduce quality of life. Unhealthy food habits and lifestyle play a major role in causing obesity. This study aimed to assess the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) among obese individuals regarding obesity, its health risks, and lifestyle modifications. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 100 obese individuals using a structured KAP questionnaire. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to determine trends and correlations between KAP scores and sociodemographic factors. The results showed that 83% had moderate knowledge about obesity, 77% demonstrated a positive attitude towards weight management, and 71% practiced healthy behaviors consistently. The findings underscore the gap between awareness and action, emphasizing the need for integrated educational and behavioral interventions.

KEYWORDS: Obesity, Knowledge Attitude Practice Questionnaire.

INTRODUCTION

An abnormal growth of adipose tissue due to an enlargement of fat cell size or an increase in fat cell number or both is called obesity.^[1] Obesity is a chronic and complex condition which affecting physical and psychological health. It significantly increases the risk of various non-

communicable diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disorders, osteoarthritis and some type of cancers.^[2] Prevalence rate of obesity in Maharashtra is 16.6%.^[3] But the prevalence of Obesity worldwide has dramatically increased due to Modernization and Rapid urbanization. Despite growing awareness, many individuals lack accurate knowledge or hold misconceptions about obesity and its management. Moreover, attitudes and practices related to healthy living often do not align with preventive or corrective measures. The success of interventions depends on the individual's knowledge, attitude, and practices. This study evaluates the KAP among obese individuals to identify key barriers to effective obesity management.

AIM

To study the Knowledge, Attitude, Practices about obesity in obese individuals.

OBJECTIVE

1. To evaluate the level of knowledge of obese individuals regarding obesity and its complications.
2. To assess attitude towards weight loss and lifestyle changes.
3. To examine the actual practices followed concerning diet, exercise, and health-seeking behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

Type of study - Observational study

Population - Obese individuals selected from OPD/IPD of kayachikitsa department

Sample Size - 100 obese individuals

Duration of study - 6 Months

Location - OPD/IPD of kayachikitsa department

Data Collection Tool - Structured KAP questionnaire with sections on Knowledge (14 questions), Attitude (15 Likert-scale items), and Practice (13 behaviour-related questions).^[4]

Inclusion Criteria

1. The patient having age between 18 years to 60 years and irrespective of socioeconomic status, sex and religion.
2. The patient of obese class 1 (30.0 – 34.9 kg/m²) and obese class 2 (35.0 – 39.9 kg/m²)

Exclusion Criteria

1. The patient having Uncontrolled Hypertension, Cardiovascular disease, pregnant women and were excluded.
2. The patient of Obese class III (More than 40 kg/m²) were excluded.
3. Patients having serious cardiac, pulmonary, renal and hepatic disease etc.
4. Obesity and Hyperlipidaemia due to drugs e.g. Anticonvulsant, Beta blockers, Corticosteroid and Diuretics.
5. Patient having history of metabolic disorders like Diabetes mellitus, etc and other endocrine diseases.

Withdrawal Criteria

1. Patient not willing for participation.

Demographic Data

In this survey study total 100 participants were enrolled the demographic data is as shown in table no.1

Table No. 1: demographic data distribution.

Gender	No of Patients
Male	40
Female	60
Age	No of Patients
18-20	3
21-30	37
31-40	25
41-50	20
51-60	15
Marital Status	No of Patients
Married	73
Unmarried	27
Divorced	0
Education	No of Patients
Un	0
E	0
P	0
M	7
HS	18
G	60
Pg	15
PhD	0
Occupation	No of Patients
Student	23

Job	25
Housewife	32
Business	13
Farmer	4
Worker	3
Desh	No of Patients
Jangala	0
Sadharan	71
Anupa	29
Socio – Economic Status	No of Patients
VP	0
LM	7
M	80
UM	13
R	0

RESULT

The survey on total 42 questions about knowledge, attitude and practices among obese individuals was carried out, and the results are as in table no.2

Table No. 2: Questionnaire about knowledge, attitude and practices among obese individuals.

Questionnaire	
Knowledge	
Que 1	Obesity can be assessed by an entity called BMI
Que 2	More fat over abdomen is dangerous than overall increase in the distribution of fat in terms of causing increased cardiovascular
Que 3	Obesity is associated with heart diseases, such as heart attack, increased blood pressure, increased cholesterol levels, etc
Que 4	Obesity is associated with diabetes
Que 5	Obesity is associated with osteoarthritis (joint problems)
Que 6	Fasting/skipping meals is a good way to lose weight
Que 7	Excess sugar consumption in the form of sweets; additional sugars in coffee/tea/milk etc., is an important risk factor which leads to overweight/obesity
Que 8	Frequent consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (pepsi/coca-cola/sweetened juices, etc.) leads to weight gain
Que 9	Frequent fried food consumption (samosa, fries, wafers, etc.) leads to weight gain
Que 10	Excessive consumption of refined foods (bread/biscuits/momos, etc.) leads to weight gain
Que 11	Constant stress is a risk factor which leads to weight gain
Que 12	Regular aerobic exercises, such as running, jogging, swimming, playing outdoor sports, etc., is an important way of losing weight

Que 13	Anti-obesity drugs are the preferred way of reducing weight
Que 14	Meal replacers/supplements are a healthy way to lose weight
Attitude	
Que 15	I consider myself obese
Que 16	consider my current weight to be harmful for my health
Que 17	I am motivated to lose weight
Que 18	I find it difficult to keep my weight steady
Que 19	I consider regular breakfast intake to be a part of healthy lifestyle.
Que 20	I consider small and frequent meals help in weight reduction.
Que 21	I am confident that I would reduce sugars/sweets in my diet
Que 22	I am confident that I would avoid fried foods
Que 23	I am confident that I would prefer salads/low calorie snacks instead of sweets/fried foods/refined foods in my diet
Que 24	I am satisfied of my current physical activity level
Que 25	I am confident that I would do physical activities such as jogging, bicycling, swimming, competitive sports, or any other activity that makes me healthy
Que 26	I am confident that I would engage in some sort of household activities when I am free
Que 27	I am confident that I would use stairs instead of lift
Que 28	I am confident that I would go to nearby places by walk
Practice	
Que 29	I am confident that I would go to nearby places by walk
Que 30	I add additional sugars in my coffee/tea/buttermilk
Que 31	I take sweet dish after meals
Que 32	I use helpers for my household activities
Que 33	I eat in response to stress
Que 34	I drink sugar sweetened beverages
Que 35	I consume fried foods
Que 36	How often do you take three major meals and two minor meals in a week
Que 37	Apart from the three major meals and two minor meals, how many snacks do you usually consume in a day?
Que 38	I include fruits/salads in my diet
Que 39	How frequently do you exercise?
Que 40	For how long do you exercise in a day?
Que 41	I consult my doctor/dietitian for weight reduction
Que 42	I am confident that I would go to nearby places by walk

Table No. 3: Result of Gradation for question number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 19, 20.

	Question numbers															
	knowledge												Attitude			
Gradation	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	9	10	11	12	15	16	19	20	
Definitely	5	34	50	75	57	92	94	94	96	86	17	95	89	82	63	50
Probably	4	21	32	21	30	6	6	6	4	14	30	4	9	15	33	40
Probably	3	1	4	1	5	1	0	0	0	0	16	1	1	2	2	8
Definitely	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	1	1	1
Don't know	1	44	14	3	8	1	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	1	1

Table No. 4: Result of Gradation for question number 6, 13, 14.

		Question numbers		
		knowledge		
Gradation		Que 6	Que 13	Que 14
Definitely	1	18	2	2
Probably	2	47	11	10
Probably not	3	15	19	12
Definitely Not	4	18	49	54
Don't know	5	2	19	22

Table No. 5: Result of Gradation for question number 21, 22, 23,25, 26, 27, 28.

		Question numbers						
		Attitude						
Gradation		21	22	23	25	26	27	28
Extremely confident	5	2	3	8	6	3	4	11
Very confident	4	33	32	41	22	44	62	72
Moderately confident	3	60	59	49	67	50	29	15
Slightly confident	2	4	6	2	4	2	4	2
Not at all confident	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0

Table No. 6: Result of Gradation for question number 24.

Que 24	I am satisfied of my current physical activity level		
Gradation		No of patients	
Very satisfied	1	2	
Satisfied	2	22	
Neither	3	51	
Dissatisfied	4	25	
Very dissatisfied	5	0	

Table No. 7: Result of Gradation for question number 18, 29, 30, 31.

		Question numbers			
		Attitude		Practice	
Gradation		Que 18	Que 29	Que 30	Que 31
Always	1	9	7	0	3
Very often	2	64	20	6	8
Sometimes	3	22	54	27	56
Rarely	4	5	13	33	32
Never	5	0	6	34	1

Table No. 8: Result of Gradation for question number 17, 32, 41.

		Question numbers		
		Attitude	Practice	
Gradation		Que 17	Que 32	Que 41
Always	5	6	3	4
Very often	4	28	9	10
Sometimes	3	57	36	58

Rarely	2	8	23	22
Never	1	1	29	6

Table No. 9: Result of Gradation for question number 33.

Que 33	I eat in response to stress			
	Gradation		No of patients	
	All the time		1	4
	Most often		2	10
	Some of the time		3	27
	Seldom		4	1
	Never		5	58

Table No. 10: Result of Gradation for question number 34, 35.

		Question numbers	
		Practice	
Gradation		Que 34	Que 35
Never	5	13	2
Rarely	4	40	39
1-2/week	3	28	52
2-3/week	2	17	6
>3/week	1	2	1

Table No. 11: Result of Gradation for question number 36.

Que 36	How often do you take three major meals and two minor meals in a week?		
	Gradation		No of patients
	All 7 days a week		5
	5-6 times a week		4
	3-4 times a week		3
	Once a week		2
	Never		1
			7
			76
			15
			2
			0

Table No. 12: Result of Gradation for question number 37.

Que	Apart from the three major meals and two minor meals, how many snacks do you		
	Gradation		No of patients
	0	5	5
	1	4	48
	2	3	40
	3	2	7
	More than 3	1	0

Table No.13 - Result of Gradation for question number 38.

Que 38	I include fruits/salads in my diet		
	Gradation		No of patients
	More than once a day		5
	4-6 times a week		4
	1-3times a week		3
			9
			49
			37

	Once in 15 days	2	4
	Never	1	1

Table No. 14: Result of Gradation for question number 39.

Que 39	How frequently do you exercise?		
	Gradation	No of patients	
	everyday	5	23
	4-6 times / week	4	19
	1-3 times / week	3	46
	once a month	2	7
	never	1	5

Table No. 15: Result of Gradation for question number 40.

Que 40	For how long do you exercise in a day?		
	Gradation	No of patients	
	Not at all	1	6
	< 15 mins	2	29
	15-30 mins	3	62
	30-60 mins	4	3
	> 60 mins	5	0

Table No. 16: Result of Gradation for question number 42.

Que 42	Which of the following statements best applies to you.		
	Gradation	No of patients	
	I currently exercise regularly and have done so for more than 6	5	5
	In the last 6 months I have started exercising regularly	4	17
	I currently exercise but not regularly	3	73
	I currently don't exercise & intend to start regular exercise in	2	4
	I currently don't exercise & do not intend to start regular	1	1

DISCUSSION

As obesity is strongly associated with unhealthy food choices, high calorie diets, fried foods, and sugar sweet beverages etc.^[5] This survey study reveals that the majority of participants were aware of the association between obesity and dietary habits that contribute to obesity. But participants often fail to translate this knowledge into practice. It was observed that only few participants are aware about BMI and its relation to obesity. Notably, constant stress emerged as a significant factor contributing to weight gain,^[6] yet most participants were unaware of this relationship.

A substantial proportion of participants recognise the importance of aerobic exercise such as running, jogging and outdoor sports for weight loss. However, despite the knowledge few participants reported confidence in engaging in these activities regularly.

Specifically, this study suggests that targeted interventions should focus on bridging the gap between Knowledge and practice, also attitude towards Obesity, addressing the impact of stress on weight gain, and promoting regular physical activity.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of understanding the knowledge, attitudes and practices of obese individuals to effectively promote the healthy lifestyle behaviors. By exploring these factors, the study showed that 83% participants had moderate knowledge about obesity and its associated health risks, and 77% demonstrated a positive attitude towards weight management, only 71% practiced healthy behaviors consistently. These results indicate a disparity between knowledge, attitude, and actual practice, and suggest the development of targeted interventions and behavior modification strategies to support obese individuals in achieving and maintaining a healthy weight.

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